

**AN OVERVIEW ON RECENT DEVELOPMENTS, CHEMICAL SYNTHESIS AND
APPLICATIONS IN NANO-TECHNOLOGY**

ABSTRACT

Recently there is a rapid increase in interest in nanotechnology as the use of nanoparticles has profound effect in commercial applications. However, little is known about the outcome and deeds of engineered nanoparticles in the environment. Submicroscopic size of nano particles results in their unique material characteristics, and manufactured nanoparticles find practical applications in a variety of areas. Chemistry has played a major role in developing the materials with new and technologically important properties. The advantage of chemical synthesis is its versatility in designing and synthesizing new materials that can be refined into desired final products.

Keywords- nanoparticles, synthesis, properties, SEM, XRD

INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticles are incredibly small, having one dimension that measures 100 nanometers or less, it would take eight hundred 100 nanometer particles side by side to match the width of a human hair. The properties of many conventional materials change when formed from nanoparticles. This is typically because nanoparticles have a greater surface area per weight than larger particles which causes them to be more reactive to some other molecules. Nature has enough evidence of nanotechnology, based on its ability to work at the atomic, molecular and supra molecular levels. The mechanisms of the biological and physical world operate mainly at the range

of 1 to 100 nm. The diameter of a hydrogen atom is about 0.1 nm which is too small to be seen with human eyes. A molecule (such as water molecule) may be made up of 20 to 30 atoms and has a diameter of about 1 nm. The width of a DNA molecule is about 2.5 nm, a typical protein is between 1 to 20 nm and ATP biochemical motor is 10 nm in diameter. The human hair is about 10,000 nm thick while human cells range from 5,000 to 200,000 nm in size. Although this is larger than nanoscale, the viruses that attack human cells fall within 10 to 200 nm, which is within the nanometre region [1,2].

Although nanotechnology is a relatively recent development in scientific research, the development of its central concepts happened over a longer period of time. Most definitions revolve around the study and control of phenomena and materials at length scales below 100 nm and quite often they make a comparison with a human hair, which is about 80,000 nm wide. There has been much debate on the future implications of nanotechnology. Nanotechnology has the potential to create many new materials and devices with a vast range of applications, such as in medicine, electronics and energy production.

Nanotechnology plays an important role in various chemical processes. Catalysis and filtration techniques are two prominent examples where nanotechnology already plays a role. The synthesis provides novel materials with tailored features and chemical properties: for example, nano-particles with a distinct chemical surrounding (ligands), or specific optical properties. In this sense, chemistry is indeed a basic nanoscience [3-5]. In a short-term perspective, chemistry will provide novel “nanomaterials” and in the long run, superior processes such as “self-assembly” will enable energy and time preserving strategies. In a sense, all chemical synthesis can be understood

in terms of nanotechnology, because of its ability to manufacture certain molecules. Thus, chemistry forms a base for nanotechnology providing tailor-made molecules, polymers, etc. as well as clusters and nanoparticles.

The primary advantage is that chemical methods offers mixing at molecular level. Chemists make new forms of matter (and they are really the only scientists to do so routinely) by joining atoms and groups of atoms together with bonds. They carry out this subnanometer-scale activity—chemical synthesis—on megaton scales when necessary, and do so with remarkable economy and safety. New and potentially commercial technologies comes out from revolutionary nanoscience seem, in fact, to be in materials science; and materials are usually the products of chemical processes[6,7]. In this context nanoparticles synthesis and their characterization becomes very important.

The properties of many conventional materials change when formed from nanoparticles. This is typically because nanoparticles have a greater surface area per weight than larger particles which causes them to be more reactive to some other molecules. However the benefits of employing simple and cost effective chemical processing methods are widely recognized and appreciated. The properties and application of nanoparticles are largely dependent on their size, shape and textures. Recently considerable attention has been drawn towards the size and shape controlled synthesis of nanostructured materials. Depending upon the specific requirements such as material to be synthesized, the grain size and maximum permissible size distribution, purity of sample required, quality of sample generated etc., different methods are employed for synthesizing

nanophase materials. The opportunities for chemistry to make important contributions to nanoscience flourish. Major five areas of nanotechnology includes 1) Synthesis of Nanostructures: Chemistry is unique in the sophistication of its ability to synthesize new forms of matter [8-10]. The invention of new kinds of nanostructures will be crucial to the discovery of new phenomena. In nanoscience, chemistry can be on the streets at the beginning of the revolution if it has the courage to do so; 2) Materials: Materials science and chemistry are, over much of their shared border, indistinguishable. Chemistry has contributed (and will continue to contribute) to the invention and development of materials whose properties depend on nanoscale structure. Chemistry and chemical engineering will, ultimately, be important in producing these materials reproducibly, economically, and in quantity; 3) Molecular Mechanisms in Nanobiology: By understanding the molecular mechanisms of functional nanostructures in biology—the light-harvesting apparatus of plants, ATPases, the ribosome, the structures that package DNA—ultimately, the cell is an area where chemistry, with its singular understanding of molecular mechanism, can make unique contributions ; 4) Tools and Analytical Methods: The scanning probe microscope—invented by Binnig and Rohrer at the IBM laboratory in Zurich—is the instrument that ignited the explosion of nanoscience. Developing new nanostructures requires knowing what they are. Physical and analytical chemistry will help to build the tools that define these structures; 5) Risk Assessment and Evaluation of Safety: Understanding the risks of nanostructures and nanomaterials will require cooperation across disciplines that range from chemistry to physiology, and from molecular medicine to epidemiology[2].

Nanoparticles are used, or being evaluated for use, in many fields. Fig. 1 highlights the broad fields/ applications of nanoparticles. Because of their submicroscopic size, they have unique material characteristics, and manufactured nanoparticles may find practical applications in a variety of areas, including medicine, engineering, catalysis, and environmental remediation as highlighted in the figure [3].

Fig.1

Preparation of nanoparticles- Nanoparticles research is currently an area of intense scientific interest due to a wide variety of potential applications in biomedical, optical & electronic fields. Recently preparation of nanoparticles becomes very significance and has got immense application in various fields. Selection of appropriate method for the preparation of nanoparticles depends on the physicochemical character of the polymer and the drug to be loaded - The primary manufacturing methods of nanoparticles from preformed polymer includes Emulsion-Solvent

Evaporation Method, salting out method, thermal decomposition method. Thermal decomposition method is cost effective and comparatively easy to achieve. With this view, silver and iron nanoparticles has been synthesized from plant extracts. These are characterized by UV- Vis, and IR spectroscopy, SEM and XRD analysis and are shown in Fig 1-4. The optical measurement of UV-visible spectrophotometer has different absorbance peak like 410nm when treated with the Nerium Obander plant extract after addition of aqueous 1mM Silver nitrate solution[11]. In case of Azadirachta indica_get synthesized with Iron nano particles by suitable surface Plasmon resonance with high band intensities and peaks was found through UV-visible spectroscopy at the range of 216- 265 nm[12]. Xray diffraction analysis with various nanoparticles has been studied by various research workers to find the high crystallinity of the prepared sample [13]. These techniques namely SEM and TEM mainly used for morphological studies of nanoparticles. Many researchers used these techniques to show that the synthesized nanoparticles were more or less uniform in size and shape[14]. In addition of these techniques their advance version are also available which gives complete idea about the synthesized nanoparticles. Silver and iron nanoparticles which has been synthesized in the laboratory are characterized by UV-Vis, IR spectroscopy and XRD analysis and are shown in Fig 1-5. In addition to these SEM analysis has also been made.

Fig.2

Fig. 3

11/20/2019	HV	mag	WD	spot	det	5 μm
12:39:11 PM	15.00 kV	10 000 x	9.9 mm	4.0	ETD	IIITDM Jabalpur

11/20/2019	HV	mag	WD	spot	det	40 µm
12:47:41 PM	15.00 kV	1 500 x	10.0 mm	4.0	ETD	IIITDM Jabalpur

UV-Vis spectra shows the absorbance of these particles at 228nm and 243 nm respectively (Fig. 1). XRD spectra show the amorphous and crystalline nature of synthesized particles (Fig. 2,3). SEM images highlights the change in structure and size from nanogranel to nanorods and 10 to 100 nm respectively (Fig. 4-6).

Above discussion clearly reveals that nanoscience is one of the most important researches in modern science. Some of the common as well as important advantages of nano particles in medical field are as under: Carrying capacity of nanoparticles is high, Shelf-stability of drug increases, Ability to sustain and control drug release patterns, Suitable for combination therapy where two or more drug can be co-delivered, Both hydrophobic and hydrophilic drug can be incorporated, System increases the bioavailability of drugs, Imaging studies can be done by utilizing them, It is used for targeted drug delivery of drugs, Development of new medicines which are safer [15,16].

Conclusion: Properties of bulk materials change when transformed in to nanoparticles and thus, finds application in many fields. The detailed study of the applications clearly explores the significance of nanoparticles in almost all fields specifically in industries & pharmaceuticals. Recent development in the field of nanosciences, by the use of chemistry and various sub branches, will be helpful in exploring unique properties with diverse applications It has also pronounced effect in day today life however it is necessary to mention here that such studies are very extensive and provides a way for upcoming projects.

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